

Archivos - Metric Custom - JQ

Carpeta: custom-metrics

ckMetrics.metrics.js

```
const state = {
  name: 'Chidamber & Kemerer Metrics Suite',
  description: 'Implements C&K metrics: WMC, DIT, NOC, CBO, RFC, LCOM',
  result: {},
  id: 'ck-metrics',
  dependencies: ['classes-per-file', 'class-coupling', 'cyclomatic-complexity'],
  status: false
}

/**
 * Calculate Weighted Methods per Class (WMC)
 * Sum of complexities of all methods in a class
 */
function calculateWMC (className, filePath, complexityData) {
  let wmc = 0

  // complexityData is already the result map (file paths as keys)
  if (complexityData &&
    complexityData[filePath] &&
    complexityData[filePath].classes &&
    complexityData[filePath].classes[className]) {
    const methods = complexityData[filePath].classes[className]
    for (const methodName in methods) {
      wmc += methods[methodName].complexity || 1
    }
  }
}
```

```

return wmc
}

/**
 * Calculate Depth of Inheritance Tree (DIT)
 * Maximum inheritance path from class to root
 * Iterative version to prevent stack overflow - O(n) with memoization
 */
function calculateDIT (className, filePath, classesData, cache = new Map
()) {
  // Check cache first - O(1)
  if (cache.has(className)) {
    return cache.get(className)
  }

  let dit = 0
  const visited = new Set()
  const stack = [{ class: className, depth: 0 }]
  let maxDepth = 0

  while (stack.length > 0) {
    const { class: currentClass, depth } = stack.pop()

    // Prevent circular inheritance
    if (visited.has(currentClass)) continue
    visited.add(currentClass)

    maxDepth = Math.max(maxDepth, depth)

    // Find parent class
    let parentFound = false
    for (const file in classesData) {
      if (classesData[file][currentClass]) {
        const classNodes = classesData[file][currentClass]

        if (Array.isArray(classNodes) && classNodes.length > 0) {
          const firstNode = classNodes[0]

```

```

    if (firstNode.parentPath && firstNode.parentPath.node && firstNode.p
arentPath.node.superClass) {
      const superClass = firstNode.parentPath.node.superClass

      if (superClass.type === 'Identifier' && superClass.name) {
        stack.push({ class: superClass.name, depth: depth + 1 })
        parentFound = true
      }
    }
  }
  break
}
}
}

```

```

// Cache result
cache.set(className, maxDepth)
return maxDepth
}

```

```

/**
 * Calculate Number of Children (NOC)
 * Number of immediate subclasses
 */
function calculateNOC (className, classesData) {
  let noc = 0

  for (const file in classesData) {
    for (const potentialChild in classesData[file]) {
      const classNodes = classesData[file][potentialChild]

      if (Array.isArray(classNodes) && classNodes.length > 0) {
        const firstNode = classNodes[0]

        if (firstNode.parentPath && firstNode.parentPath.node && firstNode.pa
rentPath.node.superClass) {
          const superClass = firstNode.parentPath.node.superClass

```

```

        if (superClass.type === 'Identifier' && superClass.name === className) {
            noc++
        }
    }
}
}

return noc
}

/**
 * Calculate Coupling Between Objects (CBO)
 * Number of distinct classes this class is coupled to
 */
function calculateCBO (className, filePath, couplingData) {
    const coupledClasses = new Set()

    if (couplingData[filePath] && couplingData[filePath][className]) {
        const classMethods = couplingData[filePath][className]

        for (const method of classMethods) {
            // Fan-out coupling
            if (method['fan-out']) {
                for (const coupledClass in method['fan-out']) {
                    if (coupledClass !== className) {
                        coupledClasses.add(coupledClass)
                    }
                }
            }
        }

        // Fan-in coupling
        if (method['fan-in']) {
            for (const coupledClass in method['fan-in']) {
                if (coupledClass !== className) {
                    coupledClasses.add(coupledClass)
                }
            }
        }
    }
}

```

```

    }
  }
}
}

return coupledClasses.size
}

/**
 * Calculate Response For a Class (RFC)
 * Number of methods that can be invoked in response to a message
 * Uses Set for O(1) lookups
 */
function calculateRFC (className, filePath, classesData, couplingData) {
  const methods = new Set()

  // Add own methods - O(m) where m is methods count
  if (classesData[filePath] && classesData[filePath][className]) {
    const classMethods = classesData[filePath][className]
    classMethods.forEach((method, index) => {
      methods.add(`${className}.${index}`)
    })
  }

  // Add methods called from this class - O(n) with Set operations
  if (couplingData[filePath] && couplingData[filePath][className]) {
    const classMethods = couplingData[filePath][className]

    for (const method of classMethods) {
      if (method['fan-out']) {
        for (const calledClass in method['fan-out']) {
          for (const calledMethod in method['fan-out'][calledClass]) {
            methods.add(`${calledClass}.${calledMethod}`)
          }
        }
      }
    }
  }
}

```

```

    }

    return methods.size
  }

  /**
   * Calculate Lack of Cohesion in Methods (LCOM)
   * LCOM1 variant: pairs of methods that don't share attributes
   * Optimized to use Maps for O(1) lookups
   */
  function calculateLCOM (className, filePath, classesData) {
    if (!classesData[filePath] || !classesData[filePath][className]) {
      return 0
    }

    const classMethods = classesData[filePath][className]
    const methodCount = classMethods.length

    if (methodCount <= 1) return 0

    // Track which attributes each method accesses - use Set for O(1) lookup
    const methodAttributes = []

    for (const methodNode of classMethods) {
      const attributes = new Set()

      // Traverse method to find attribute accesses
      if (methodNode.body) {
        traverseNode(methodNode.body, (node) => {
          // this.attribute patterns - direct check, O(1)
          if (node.type === 'MemberExpression' &&
            node.object && node.object.type === 'ThisExpression' &&
            node.property && node.property.name) {
            attributes.add(node.property.name)
          }
        })
      }
    }
  }

```

```

    methodAttributes.push(attributes)
  }

  // Count pairs with no shared attributes - O(n^2m) where m is avg attribute
  s
  let pairsWithNoSharing = 0
  let pairsWithSharing = 0

  for (let i = 0; i < methodCount; i++) {
    for (let j = i + 1; j < methodCount; j++) {
      // Use Set.has() for O(1) lookup
      const shared = [...methodAttributes[i]].some(attr => methodAttributes[j].
has(attr))

      if (shared) {
        pairsWithSharing++
      } else {
        pairsWithNoSharing++
      }
    }
  }

  return Math.max(0, pairsWithNoSharing - pairsWithSharing)
}

/**
 * Helper function to traverse AST node iteratively (no recursion)
 */
function traverseNode (node, callback) {
  if (!node || typeof node !== 'object') return

  // Use stack for iterative traversal - O(n) time, prevents stack overflow
  const stack = [node]

  while (stack.length > 0) {
    const current = stack.pop()
    if (!current || typeof current !== 'object') continue

```

```

callback(current)

// Push children to stack
for (const key in current) {
  if (key === 'parentPath' || key === 'parent') continue

  const child = current[key]
  if (Array.isArray(child)) {
    // Push in reverse order to maintain traversal order
    for (let i = child.length - 1; i >= 0; i--) {
      if (child[i]) stack.push(child[i])
    }
  } else if (child && typeof child === 'object') {
    stack.push(child)
  }
}
}
}

const visitors = {
  Program (path) {
    state.currentFile = path.node.filePath

    if (!state.result[state.currentFile]) {
      state.result[state.currentFile] = {}
    }
  },

  ClassDeclaration (path) {
    const node = path.node

    if (!node.id || !node.id.name) return

    const className = node.id.name
    const filePath = state.currentFile

    const classesData = state.dependencies['classes-per-file']
    const couplingData = state.dependencies['class-coupling']

```

```

const complexityData = state.dependencies['cyclomatic-complexity']

state.result[filePath][className] = {
  wmc: calculateWMC(className, filePath, complexityData),
  //dit: calculateDIT(className, filePath, classesData),
  //noc: calculateNOC(className, classesData),
  cbo: calculateCBO(className, filePath, couplingData),
  rfc: calculateRFC(className, filePath, classesData, couplingData),
  lcom: calculateLCOM(className, filePath, classesData)
}
},

ClassExpression (path) {
  const parentPath = path.parentPath

  if (parentPath.node.type === 'VariableDeclarator' && parentPath.node.id
  && parentPath.node.id.name) {
    const className = parentPath.node.id.name
    const filePath = state.currentFile

    const classesData = state.dependencies['classes-per-file']
    const couplingData = state.dependencies['class-coupling']
    const complexityData = state.dependencies['cyclomatic-complexity']

    state.result[filePath][className] = {
      wmc: calculateWMC(className, filePath, complexityData),
      //dit: calculateDIT(className, filePath, classesData),
      //noc: calculateNOC(className, classesData),
      cbo: calculateCBO(className, filePath, couplingData),
      rfc: calculateRFC(className, filePath, classesData, couplingData),
      lcom: calculateLCOM(className, filePath, classesData)
    }
  }
}
}

function postProcessing (state) {
  delete state.currentFile
}

```

```
delete state.dependencies
state.status = true
}

export { state, visitors, postProcessing }
```

CyclomaticComplexity.metric.js

```
const state = {
  name: 'Cyclomatic Complexity',
  description: 'Calculates McCabe Cyclomatic Complexity for each function
and class method',
  result: {},
  id: 'cyclomatic-complexity',
  dependencies: ['functions-per-file', 'classes-per-file'],
  status: false
}

/**
 * Calculate cyclomatic complexity for a given path
 * Complexity = 1 (base) + number of decision points
 * Iterative traversal to prevent stack overflow - O(n)
 */
function calculateComplexity (path) {
  let complexity = 1

  // Use iterative stack-based traversal
  const nodesToVisit = [path.node]
  const nodeTypeCounters = {
    IfStatement: 0,
    ConditionalExpression: 0,
    ForStatement: 0,
    ForInStatement: 0,
    ForOfStatement: 0,
    WhileStatement: 0,
    DoWhileStatement: 0,
    SwitchCase: 0,
    LogicalExpression: 0,
```

```

    CatchClause: 0
  }

while (nodesToVisit.length > 0) {
  const node = nodesToVisit.pop()
  if (!node || typeof node !== 'object') continue

  // Count decision points - O(1) per node
  if (node.type === 'IfStatement') complexity++
  else if (node.type === 'ConditionalExpression') complexity++
  else if (node.type === 'ForStatement') complexity++
  else if (node.type === 'ForInStatement') complexity++
  else if (node.type === 'ForOfStatement') complexity++
  else if (node.type === 'WhileStatement') complexity++
  else if (node.type === 'DoWhileStatement') complexity++
  else if (node.type === 'SwitchCase' && node.test !== null) complexity++
  else if (node.type === 'LogicalExpression' && (node.operator === '&&' ||
node.operator === '||')) complexity++
  else if (node.type === 'CatchClause') complexity++

  // Add children to stack
  for (const key in node) {
    if (key === 'parentPath' || key === 'parent' || key === 'loc') continue

    const child = node[key]
    if (Array.isArray(child)) {
      for (let i = child.length - 1; i >= 0; i--) {
        if (child[i]) nodesToVisit.push(child[i])
      }
    } else if (child && typeof child === 'object') {
      nodesToVisit.push(child)
    }
  }
}

return complexity
}

```

```

const visitors = {
  Program (path) {
    state.currentFile = path.node.filePath

    if (!state.result[state.currentFile]) {
      state.result[state.currentFile] = {
        functions: {},
        classes: {}
      }
    }
  },

  // Function declarations
  FunctionDeclaration (path) {
    if (!path.node.id || !path.node.id.name) return

    const functionName = path.node.id.name
    const complexity = calculateComplexity(path)

    if (!state.result[state.currentFile].functions[functionName]) {
      state.result[state.currentFile].functions[functionName] = {}
    }

    state.result[state.currentFile].functions[functionName].complexity = com
    plexity
  },

  // Function expressions
  FunctionExpression (path) {
    let functionName = ''

    if (path.parentPath.node.type === 'VariableDeclarator' && path.parentPa
    th.node.id.name) {
      functionName = path.parentPath.node.id.name
    } else return

    const complexity = calculateComplexity(path)

```

```

if (!state.result[state.currentFile].functions[functionName]) {
  state.result[state.currentFile].functions[functionName] = {}
}

state.result[state.currentFile].functions[functionName].complexity = com
plexity
},

// Arrow functions
ArrowFunctionExpression (path) {
  if (!path.parentPath.node.id || !path.parentPath.node.id.name) return

  const functionName = path.parentPath.node.id.name
  const complexity = calculateComplexity(path)

  if (!state.result[state.currentFile].functions[functionName]) {
    state.result[state.currentFile].functions[functionName] = {}
  }

  state.result[state.currentFile].functions[functionName].complexity = com
plexity
},

// Class methods
ClassDeclaration (path) {
  const node = path.node

  if (!node.id || !node.id.name) return

  const className = node.id.name

  if (!state.result[state.currentFile].classes[className]) {
    state.result[state.currentFile].classes[className] = {}
  }

  path.traverse({
    ClassMethod (methodPath) {
      const methodName = methodPath.node.key.name || (methodPath.nod

```



```

plexity = complexity
    }
  })
}
}
}

function postProcessing (state) {
  delete state.currentFile
  delete state.dependencies
  state.status = true
}

export { state, visitors, postProcessing }

```

fout.metric.js

```

const state = {
  name: 'Module Fan-Out',
  description: 'Calculates Fan-Out (FOUT) - number of distinct modules imported by each file',
  result: {},
  id: 'fout',
  dependencies: ['files'],
  status: false
}

const visitors = {
  Program (path) {
    state.currentFile = path.node.filePath

    if (!state.result[state.currentFile]) {
      state.result[state.currentFile] = {}
    }

    // Set to track unique imports
    state.currentImports = new Set()
  },

```

```

// ES6 import statements
ImportDeclaration (path) {
  const source = path.node.source.value
  state.currentImports.add(source)
},

// CommonJS require calls
CallExpression (path) {
  // Detect require('module')
  if (path.node.callee.name === 'require' &&
    path.node.arguments.length > 0 &&
    path.node.arguments[0].type === 'StringLiteral') {
    const source = path.node.arguments[0].value
    state.currentImports.add(source)
  }

  // Detect import('module') - dynamic imports
  if (path.node.callee.type === 'Import' &&
    path.node.arguments.length > 0 &&
    path.node.arguments[0].type === 'StringLiteral') {
    const source = path.node.arguments[0].value
    state.currentImports.add(source)
  }
},

exit (path) {
  if (path.type === 'Program') {
    const imports = Array.from(state.currentImports)
    state.result[state.currentFile] = {
      fout: state.currentImports.size,
      imports
    }
  }
}

function postProcessing (state) {

```

```
delete state.currentImports
delete state.currentFile
delete state.dependencies
state.status = true
}

export { state, visitors, postProcessing }
```

JQ-queries.md

JQ Queries for results.json Analysis

This document contains reusable JQ queries for analyzing `results.json` files across all projects.

Results.json Structure

The `results.json` file contains the following top-level keys:

- **files**: List of analyzed files
- **errors**: Categorized errors (file, parse, metric, traverse)
- **ck-metrics**: Chidamber-Kemerer metrics per file
- **class-coupling**: Class-level coupling analysis
- **classes-per-file**: Number of classes per file
- **cyclomatic-complexity**: Cyclomatic complexity per function/class
- **file-coupling**: File-level coupling (imports/dependencies)
- **fout**: Fan-out metric
- **function-coupling**: Function-level coupling
- **functions-per-file**: Number of functions per file

Basic Structure Queries

Get all top-level keys

```
```bash
jq 'keys | sort' results.json
```
```

Get specific metric structure

```

``bash
jq '["ck-metrics"] | keys' results.json
jq '["class-coupling"] | keys' results.json
jq '["cyclomatic-complexity"] | keys' results.json
...

## Files Analysis

### Get total number of files
``bash
jq '.files.result | length' results.json
...

### Get list of all files
``bash
jq '.files.result' results.json
...

### Get files with specific extension
``bash
jq '.files.result | map(select(endswith(".ts")))' results.json
jq '.files.result | map(select(endswith(".js")))' results.json
...

### Count files by extension
``bash
jq '.files.result | group_by(split(".") | .[-1]) | map({extension: .[0] | split(".") | .[-1], count: length})' results.json
...

## Error Analysis

### Get error summary
``bash
jq '.errors | {file: (.file | length), parse: (.parse | length), metric: (.metric | length), traverse: (.traverse | length)}' results.json
...

```

```
### Get all file errors
```

```
``bash  
jq '.errors.file' results.json  
...
```

```
### Get all parse errors
```

```
``bash  
jq '.errors.parse' results.json  
...
```

```
### Get all metric errors
```

```
``bash  
jq '.errors.metric' results.json  
...
```

```
### Get all traverse errors
```

```
``bash  
jq '.errors.traverse' results.json  
...
```

```
### Count errors by type
```

```
``bash  
jq '.errors | to_entries | map({type: .key, count: (.value | length)})' results.js  
on  
...
```

```
## Metric Status Queries
```

```
### Get all metric statuses
```

```
``bash  
jq '{  
  "ck-metrics": .["ck-metrics"].status,  
  "class-coupling": .["class-coupling"].status,  
  "classes-per-file": .["classes-per-file"].status,  
  "cyclomatic-complexity": .["cyclomatic-complexity"].status,  
  "file-coupling": .["file-coupling"].status,  
  "fout": .fout.status,  
  "function-coupling": .["function-coupling"].status,  
}
```

```

"functions-per-file": .["functions-per-file"].status
}' results.json
...

### Check if all metrics succeeded
```bash
jq '["ck-metrics"].status, .["class-coupling"].status, .["cyclomatic-comple
xity"].status, .["file-coupling"].status, .f.out.status, .["function-coupling"].st
atus] | all(. == "success")' results.json
...

Metric Results Queries

Get cyclomatic complexity result type
```bash
jq '["cyclomatic-complexity"].result | type' results.json
...

### Get first file in cyclomatic complexity results
```bash
jq '["cyclomatic-complexity"].result | to_entries | .[0]' results.json
...

Get cyclomatic complexity structure for a file
```bash
jq '["cyclomatic-complexity"].result | to_entries | .[0] | {file: .key, structure:
(.value | keys)}' results.json
...

### Count files with complexity data
```bash
jq '["cyclomatic-complexity"].result | keys | length' results.json
...

Get class coupling result type
```bash
jq '["class-coupling"].result | type' results.json
...

```

```
### Get file coupling result type
```bash
jq '["file-coupling"].result | type' results.json
```
```

Coupling Metrics Explained

Class Coupling (`resultCount`)

The `resultCount` in `class-coupling` represents the **number of unique class-to-class relationships** detected in the project. Each entry indicates a dependency where one class references or uses another class. Higher counts suggest more interconnected class structures.

Function Coupling (`resultCount`)

The `resultCount` in `function-coupling` represents the **number of unique function-to-function relationships**. This measures how functions call or reference other functions within the codebase.

Fan-out (`resultCount`)

The `resultCount` in `fout` represents the **number of files/modules that have outgoing dependencies**. Fan-out measures how many external modules each file imports or depends on. High fan-out indicates files with many external dependencies.

File Coupling (`resultCount`)

The `resultCount` in `file-coupling` represents the **number of files analyzed for import/dependency relationships**. This measures the import graph structure at the file level.

Advanced Analysis Queries

Calculate average cyclomatic complexity per project

```
```bash
jq '["cyclomatic-complexity"].result | to_entries[] | .value.functions // {} | to_entries[] | .value.complexity // 0 | if length > 0 then (add / length) else 0 end' results.json
```
```

Find top 5 most complex functions in a project

```
```bash
jq '["cyclomatic-complexity"].result | to_entries[] | .value.functions // {} | to_entries[] | {file: .key, function: .key, complexity: (.value.complexity // 0)} | sort_by(-.complexity) | .[0:5]' results.json
```
```

Calculate classes per file average

```
```bash
jq '["classes-per-file"].result | to_entries[] | .value // 0 | if length > 0 then (add / length) else 0 end' results.json
```
```

Calculate functions per file average

```
```bash
jq '["functions-per-file"].result | to_entries[] | .value // 0 | if length > 0 then (add / length) else 0 end' results.json
```
```

Calculate file coupling average (imports per file)

```
```bash
jq '["file-coupling"].result | to_entries[] | .value // [] | length | if length > 0 then (add / length) else 0 end' results.json
```
```

Extract all complexity data with file paths

```
```bash
jq '["cyclomatic-complexity"].result | to_entries[] | {file: .key, functions: [.value.functions // {} | to_entries[] | {name: .key, complexity: .value.complexity}]}' results.json
```
```

Metric Status Queries

Get metric descriptions

```
```bash
jq '{
```

```
"ck-metrics": .["ck-metrics"].description,
"class-coupling": .["class-coupling"].description,
"cyclomatic-complexity": .["cyclomatic-complexity"].description,
"file-coupling": .["file-coupling"].description,
"files": .files.description,
"fout": .fout.description
}' results.json
...
```

### Create summary object

```
```bash  
jq '{  
  project: "PROJECT_NAME",  
  totalFiles: (.files.result | length),  
  errors: {  
    file: (.errors.file | length),  
    parse: (.errors.parse | length),  
    metric: (.errors.metric | length),  
    traverse: (.errors.traverse | length)  
  },  
  metricStatus: {  
    "ck-metrics": .["ck-metrics"].status,  
    "class-coupling": .["class-coupling"].status,  
    "cyclomatic-complexity": .["cyclomatic-complexity"].status,  
    "file-coupling": .["file-coupling"].status,  
    "fout": .fout.status,  
    "function-coupling": .["function-coupling"].status  
  }  
}' results.json  
...
```

Extract only successful metrics

```
```bash  
jq 'to_entries | map(select(.value.status == "success")) | from_entries' results.json
...
```

### Get files with errors in cyclomatic complexity

```
```bash
jq '["cyclomatic-complexity"].result | to_entries | map(select(.value == {} o
r .value == null)) | map(.key)' results.json
...

```

```
## Batch Processing (PowerShell)
```

```
### Run unified analysis across all projects
```

```
```powershell
.\analyze.ps1
...

```

```
Process all projects and extract custom summaries
```

```
```powershell
Get-ChildItem -Path ".\packages" -Recurse -Filter "results.json" | ForEach-
Object {
    $project = $_.Directory.Name
    jq --arg proj "$project" '{
        project: $proj,
        totalFiles: (.files.result | length),
        errorCount: ((.errors.file | length) + (.errors.parse | length) + (.errors.m
etric | length) + (.errors.traverse | length))
    }' $_.FullName
}
...

```

```
### Extract statistical data for specific metric
```

```
```powershell
Get-ChildItem -Path ".\packages" -Recurse -Filter "results.json" | ForEach-
Object {
 $project = $_.Directory.Name
 jq --arg proj "$project" '{
 project: $proj,
 avgComplexity: ([["cyclomatic-complexity"].result | to_entries[] | .valu
e.functions // {} | to_entries[] | .value.complexity // 0] | if length > 0 then (a
dd / length) else 0 end)
 }' $_.FullName
} | jq -s '!'

```

```

...

Find projects with highest complexity
```powershell
Get-ChildItem -Path ".\packages" -Recurse -Filter "results.json" | ForEach-Object {
    jq -c --arg proj $_.Directory.Name '{
        project: $proj,
        maxComplexity: ([.["cyclomatic-complexity"].result | to_entries[] | .value.functions // {} | to_entries[] | .value.complexity // 0] | if length > 0 then max else 0 end)
    }' $_.FullName
} | jq -s 'sort_by(-.maxComplexity) | .[0:10]'
...

```

Usage Examples

Single project analysis

```

```powershell
cd packages\P83-fp-ts
jq 'keys' results.json
jq '.files.result | length' results.json
...

```

### ### Run complete analysis pipeline

```

```powershell
.\analyze.ps1
...

```

View aggregated statistics

```

```powershell
Import-Csv .\aggregated-statistics.csv | Format-Table
...

```

### ### View top complex files

```

```powershell
Import-Csv .\top-complex-files.csv | Select-Object -First 10 | Format-Table
...

```

```
### Compare metrics across projects
```

```
```powershell
```

```
Import-Csv .\statistical-analysis.csv | Sort-Object avgCyclomaticComplexity -Descending | Format-Table
```

```
```
```

```
### Deep dive into specific metric
```

```
```powershell
```

```
$project = "P83-fp-ts"
```

```
jq '["cyclomatic-complexity"]' ".\packages\$project\results.json"
```

```
```
```

```
```powershell
```

```
$project = "P83-fp-ts"
```

```
jq '["cyclomatic-complexity"] | to_entries | map(.key as $fileName | .value.functions | to_entries | map({ "file": $fileName, "function": .key, "complexity": .value.complexity })) | flatten | sort_by(.complexity) | reverse' ".\packages\$project\results.json"
```

```
```
```

```
### Export to Excel-compatible format
```

```
```powershell
```

```
Import-Csv .\aggregated-statistics.csv | Export-Excel -Path analysis-results.xlsx -AutoSize -TableName Statistics
```

```
```
```